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SOME MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF F₁ HYBRIDS OBTAINED FROM INTERAMPHIPOID CROSSES INVOLVING TRITITRIGIA

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Abstract

The purpose of the research was the study of the success rate of hybridization in interamphiploid crosses with involving of trititrigia (*T. aestivum* / *Ag. junceum*) and some morphological indicators of the obtained first generation hybrids. The research was conducted according to the methodology of field experiments. The hybridization potential of wheat-alien amphiploids involved in this research and some agronomically important morphological traits of the first hybrid generation plants obtained from their hybridization were studied. The results of the study can be informative for the exploitation of wheat-alien amphiploids in various genetic studies and breeding program. Hybridization success was higher when the trititrigia form (*T. aestivum* / *Ag. junceum*) involved in interamphiploid crosses is used as a male parent. In the hybridizations conducted using trititrigia (*T. aestivum* / *Ag. junceum*), positive heterosis for spike length was observed in all F₁ plants, except for the hybrids obtained from *trititrigia* × *haynatrix* combination. The 4 wheat-alien amphiploids used in the study (*trititrigia* - *T. aestivum* / *Ag. junceum*, *haynatrix* - *T. turgidum* / *H. villosa* and local forms of triticale - AD908 and AD1164) were involved in interamphiploid hybridization for the first time as well as their derived hybrid generations studied. The local triticale form ABDR (or NA - 75) was involved in interamphiploid hybridization with trititrigia for the first time.

Keywords: Amphiploid, Trititrigia, Hybridization, Morphological traits, Heterosis

Introduction: Trititrigia (×Trititrigia *cziczinii* Tzvel.) (2n = 56) is an amphiploid or synthetic species obtained from interspecific hybridization of wheat (*Triticum* sp.) and emmer (*Elytrigia* sp.), which combines the characteristics of high adaptability and high protein-rich grain and green mass yield in one growing season [Шюклина et al., 2023; Lachuga, et al., 2023]. Wheat amphiploids play an important role in genetic research and selection, creating unique opportunities for elucidating genetic mechanisms, improving varieties, and developing new genetically determined traits [Иванова et al., 2020; Шюклина et al., 2021; Аленичева et al., 2023]. These forms were created both to study the interaction of different genomes in them and to use them as bridge species for transferring genes controlling important agricultural traits of interest to researchers and breeders to cultivated wheat varieties [Dandan Wu et al., 2024]. Despite the numerous studies on the use of alien amphiploids of wheat as bridges for transferring beneficial traits to cultivated wheat, there are few studies devoted to the creation and study of their inter-amphiploid or “bridge” hybrids [Shulyndin and Gorban, 1971; Wang G. & Wu Y, 1989; Carvalho et al., 2008]. The advantage of inter-amphiploid hybridizations is that by transferring alien gene diversity from different sources to target polygenomic forms or new wheat donors, it is possible to concentrate in them improved traits such as disease resistance, stress tolerance, and yield potential resulting from the genetic contributions of multiple synthetic bridge species. Forms with such complex traits are then used in the next facilitated transfer process [Гончаров и др., 2020].

Taking into account the above, the initial goal of our research was to obtain and study inter-amphiploid

hybrid populations using various foreign wheat amphiploids, and the final goal was to select certain polygenomic morphotypes of agricultural interest from the upper generations of the created populations. The current research work is devoted to the study of the success rate of inter-amphiploid hybridizations with the participation of trititrigia (*T. aestivum* / *Ag. junceum*) and some morphological indicators of first-generation hybrids.

Material and methods: The study was conducted at the Absheron scientific base of the Institute of Genetic Resources of the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan, under irrigated conditions (2020-2023). Five foreign amphiploids of wheat were used as starting material for hybridization: three forms of triticale - ABDR (or NA-75), AD908, AD1164, a form of trititrigia - *T. aestivum* / *Ag. junceum* (=Elytrigia *juncea* (L.) Nevski.) and haynatrix *T. turgidum* subsp. *durum* / *H. villosa*. Triticale ABDR (genome ABR, 2n = 42), AD908 (genome ABR, 2n = 42), AD1164 (genome ABD/R, 2n = 42) were created in the Molecular Cytogenetics Laboratory of the Institute of Genetic Resources, trititrigia - *T. aestivum* / *Ag. junceum* (genome 21 II [AABB]+7 II [JJ], 2n = 56) and haynatrix - *T. turgidum* / *H. villosa* (genome 14 II [AABB]+7II [VV], 2n = 42) samples were obtained from the Wheat Genetic and Genome Resource Center (WGGRC) at Kansas State University, USA.

Field experiments and structural analysis of the obtained hybrids were carried out in accordance with the methodology of field experiments on cereal plant breeding [Musayev, 2008]. During the vegetation period, the necessary agrotechnical work was carried out in the experimental field of the plants involved in interamphiploid crosses and the hybrids obtained from

them. In the first year of the study, in the first decade of November, seed materials of the parental forms intended for hybridization were sown in the experimental field, and mass emergence of seedlings was observed in the second decade of November. Interamphiploid hybridization works were carried out reciprocally in some combinations in April-May. The isolating hybridization packages on the plants that had completed physiological maturity were cut and removed, the percentage of grain setting in the spikes was determined, and the grains were placed in a refrigerator (+5°C) for use in the next planting year. In the second year of the experiment, these hybrid grains were germinated in Petri dishes at room temperature in parallel with the parental forms. After the germination percentage of the obtained hybrid grains was determined, they were transferred to open field conditions together with the seedlings of the parental forms and their viability was recorded during the vegetation period. The first generation hybrid plants that had completed physiological maturity and the parental forms were uprooted and a comparative structural analysis was performed on them according to some morphological characteristics.

Results and discussion: The results of the interamphiploid hybridizations conducted in the present study are presented in Table 1. The highest grain setting percentage was observed in the combinations trititrigia × haynatriticum and trititrigia × triticale (ABDR), where the amphiploid *T. aestivum* / *Ag. junceum* was used as the parent form. During the germination of the resulting hybrid grains, a pattern often observed in wheat hybridizations - a higher germination percentage was recorded mainly in combinations with low grain setting. The viability indicators of hybrid plants transplanted to the experimental field varied within the range of 50 - 100% for the combinations.

Some morphological characteristics of F1 hybrids obtained from interamphiploid crosses involving Trititrigia (*T. aestivum* / *Ag. junceum*)

Hybrid combinations / Parents	Plant height, cm	Spike		
		length, cm	number of spikelets	length, cm number of spikelets, pcs fertility, %
<i>T.aestivum/Ag.junceum</i> × ABDR	110,5	24	31	3
ABDR × <i>T.aestivum/Ag.junceum</i>	135	26	36	1
AD1164 × <i>T.aestivum/Ag.junceum</i>	64	17	29	2
AD908 × <i>T.aestivum/Ag.junceum</i>	124	24	31	2
<i>T.aest./Ag.jun.</i> × <i>T.turg./H.villos.</i>	134	14,5	22	4
<i>T.aestivum/Ag.junceum</i>	120	15,5	27	99
ABDR	95,47	19,03	31,67	98
AD1164	68	15	*çoxçiçəkli	≈ 70
AD908	100	16,92	36,3	96
<i>T. turgidum</i> subsp. <i>dur.</i> / <i>H. villosa</i>	94,67	15,17	21	90

Thus, the results of hybridizations using *T.aestivum/Ag.junceum* trititrigia revealed the presence of positive heterosis for spike length in all F1 plants, except for the Trititrigia × Haynatriticum combination. In other combinations, except for one combination (ABDR × *T.aestivum/Ag.junceum*), no correlation of this trait with the number of spikelets per

Among the first-generation hybrids observed in field conditions, plants that spiked 6-8 days earlier than others belonged to two combinations: *T.aestivum/Ag.junceum* × *T. turgidum* subsp. *durum/H. villosa* and AD1164 × *T.aestivum/Ag.junceum*. Although powdery mildew and yellow rust diseases were not observed in the studied hybrid plants during the vegetation period, brown rust was recorded in all hybrid plants belonging to reciprocal combinations of trititrigia with triticale, except for plants belonging to the Trititrigia × Haynatriticum combination. It should be noted that among the parent plants, all forms of triticale, unlike haynatriticum, are more or less susceptible to yellow and brown rust diseases. Trititrigia *T.aestivum/Ag.junceum* showed moderate susceptibility to leaf or yellow rust during epiphytotypic years.

After the F1 plants that had completed the vegetation period were manually harvested, structural analysis was performed on them and some of the obtained indicators are given in Table 2. As can be seen from the table, the hybrid plants varied in plant height, varying between 64 and 134 cm, and were intermediate in height between both parents, taller than at least one of them, or shorter than both parents.

Unlike the Trititrigia × Haynatriticum combination, positive heterosis was observed in spike length in all hybrid plants belonging to reciprocal combinations of trititrigia and triticale. Positive heterosis was observed in the ABDR × *T.aestivum/Ag.junceum* combination, mainly in the number of spikelets per spike. The yield of F1 hybrid plants was higher in combinations that showed more grain setting in F0.

spikelet was detected, which in turn resulted in the production of plants with sparse spikelets.

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